

science and policy
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HORIZON2020 Programme
Contract No. 733032 HBM4EU

Annex 2.1.5 to D7.3

Concept for the development of non-responder questionnaires in the scope of HBM4EU

WP 7

Task 7.3

D7.3

Version 2.0

7th November 2018

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This document has been created for the HBM4EU project. HBM4EU has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 733032.

1 Aim of this concept

One of the main goals of the HBM4EU programme is working towards the harmonisation of procedures and tools for HBM across the EU member states, its associated and partnered countries. A step towards this goal is the establishment of a European HBM platform which is foreseen to provide foundation for the design and implementation of HBM studies across Europe.

Survey design and fieldwork preparation, a key part of this HBM platform, include the development of questionnaires.

In order to aid in filling various data gaps across the partner countries, HBM4EU questionnaires are required to comply with different studies easily, e.g. entirely new studies or already existing studies which are extended with some parts to deliver comparable results in the frame of HBM4EU (see also D7.3). To fit within the limits of the HBM4EU programme, it is most likely that studies of the cross-sectional type are to be conducted or aligned. Recruitment procedures need to be adaptable to different age groups or certain target groups (occupational area, groups with high risk) and are further required to be equipped to manage the challenges of achieving representativeness. Non-responder questionnaires are a perfect instrument to collect more information on randomly selected potential participants who refrain from taking part which affects the representativeness of the study.

In this document, a concept for a non-responder questionnaire to accompany studies performed under HBM4EU is presented. Assessing non-response and addressing its reasons and effects is important when the study is aiming for a representative coverage of the population.

This concept for the development of non-responder questionnaires in the scope of HBM4EU is primarily based on experiences collected in the German Environmental Surveys (GerES), cross-sectional population representative studies. The concept addresses the reasons for and effects of non-response and aims at covering adjustment for losses and weighting and delivers a proposal for aspects which should be considered when creating a non-responder questionnaire. Finally, a proposal for a general non-response questionnaire to accompany the HBM4EU basic questionnaire on the 1st priority substances is provided.

2 Non-response

When interpreting data from a population-based study, it is important to know if there was a systematic difference of characteristics between those who took part in the study and those who declined participation in the study (O'Neill, Marsden et al. 1995).

Non-response is defined as 'failure to obtain a measurement on one or more study variables for one or more elements selected for the survey' (OECD 2002). On data, it can have two main effects. It can introduce bias (if non-respondents systematically differ from the respondents) and, due to the sample size observed being reduced from the originally planned sample size in case of non-response, it contributes to an increase in total variance of estimates (Statistics Canada 2009), i.e. increases inaccuracy of the estimates.

Low response rates are unfortunately typical for observational exposure studies (Callahan, Clickner et al. 1995). It is therefore paramount to adjust for those individuals of the gross sample who will reduce the originally planned sample size, either because they can be considered as quality-neutral loss or because they declined participation even though they were eligible for response (herein referred to as 'Eligible Respondents', see Figure 1) (Schnell 1997). Subsequently, analysis for bias needs to be performed.

The following Chapter 3.1 elaborates on how and why the gross sample needs to be adjusted for potential losses that are considered quality-neutral. This is reflected in the first level of Figure 1, in the split of the gross sample in quality-neutral losses (QNL) and Eligible Respondents. Chapter 3.1.1. provides details on the measurement of these quality-neutral losses which is tightly interconnected with the measurement of other (systematic) losses. These losses can happen at the second level of Figure 1, indicated by the split between those Eligible Respondents that accept and those that decline participation. The adjustment process for this is briefly outlined in Chapter 3.2 on weighting.

Figure 1: Schematic breakdown of the sample according to participant reaction

2.1 Adjusting the gross sample by QNL

In order to achieve a number of individuals representative for the target population's distribution of criteria (e.g. region, age, sex), a gross sample is drawn from the target population following the sampling frame, e.g. a population register or a list of schools, covering these criteria. This sample is also often referred to as original sample. More examples for sampling frames are elaborated on in the Concept for a Study Protocol (Annex 1 to Deliverable 7.3).

Examples in the following are provided mainly for situations in which population registers are used to draw the gross sample.

Every gross sample drawn is likely to have quality-neutral losses (QNL). According to the former Centre for Surveys, Methods and Analyses (ZUMA) in Germany, QNL are defined as losses of address drawn via the sampling frame that are unavailable for the study, but not due to a third person involved (e.g. the interviewer or the target person) (Porst 1996). Reasons for this can, for

example, be the specified street or house number cannot be found, the flat is uninhabited, unused addresses, or no person in the household belongs to the intended target group (VDI-3883 2015). The latter criterion can take the shape of several new criteria such as target person is older than a certain age or the communication with participant is impossible (speech impediments or language barrier) (Kamtsiuris, Lange et al. 2007).

In order to adjust the sample for these losses, the QNL are deducted from the gross sample to define those individuals that count as Eligible Respondents (see Figure 1). Like all losses, if not adjusted for, QNL can contribute to an increase in total variance of estimates due to the difference in observed and originally sought sample size (Statistics Canada 2009). It is important to define which losses are classified as ‘quality-neutral losses’ at the beginning of a survey (see Table 1).

2.1.1 Measuring QNL

There can be many different reasons why an individual that has been drawn as part of the gross sample does not end up as part of the net sample.

During the recruitment process, it is essential that the result of each contact to an address drawn for the gross sample is documented (DGEpi 2008). Codes for each possible result like ‘agreement to participate received’, or ‘no information about reasons for non-participation’ and also reasons for non-participation should be provided. It is recommended to compile a list with all such result codes in advance and define clearly which will be considered as quality-neutral loss and which will not (examples see Table 1 or table 5.1 of the report on the German national consumption survey II (MRI&BMEL 2008) included in the references). Every address or individual, depending on the sampling scheme, drawn for the gross sample should receive one of these codes. In order to make the result codes (usually numerical with a brief title) easily understandable and applicable by the study staff, they should be connected to a description at when this code has to be selected. An example for this would be if the participant expresses doubts about data protection measures in some form (despite being provided with the data protection statement) and does not wish to participate because of this, the code for ‘doubts about data protection measures’ has to be selected.

As due to ethical reasons individuals cannot be contacted again as soon as they finally decline participation, it is recommended to document these reasons already during the individual recruitment procedure. If the individual agrees, this can be combined with the application of a non-responder questionnaire.

In Table 1, some examples for result codes including possible reasons for non-participation and their typical classification (as QNL or not) are shown. They are selected for a sample that has been drawn from an address-based system, such as a population register. The list of codes has to be put together or at least adjusted for each study individually, taking specifically into account the sampling frame. Point 04 ‘Flat uninhabited’ for example would not apply if a sample is selected on individual basis.

Table 1: Examples for result codes including reasons for non-participation and definitions of QNL for an address-based sample

Number	Result code	Quality-neutral loss?
02	Agreement to participate received	-
03	No information about reasons for non-participation (e.g. no successful contact)	No
04	Flat uninhabited	Yes

05	Doubts about data protection measures	No
06	Acute or chronic illness	No
07	Not interested, not convinced by purpose of the study	No
08	Death of individual	Yes
09	Long-term absence during entire study duration	Yes
10	Moved away from the study area	Yes

2.1.2 Other losses

Examples for (systematic) losses that are not quality-neutral could be typically the refusal of participation, the termination of an interview or the inaccessibility of the target person after a set amount of contact attempts (VDI-3883 2015). Table 1 also shows three examples of losses that are typically not considered quality-neutral: illness, doubts regarding data protection and lack of interest. There are of course many more reasons which should all be considered, listed, coded and described in detail.

2.2 Weighting

‘A typical survey objective is to estimate descriptive population parameters, as well as analytical parameters, on the basis of a sample selected from a population of interest.’ (Statistics Canada 2009).

In order to estimate those parameters correctly, the sample needs to be representative of the study population.

Losses from this (gross) sample, quality-neutral or not, therefore need to be adjusted for. While QNL can be simply deducted from the gross sample (therefore providing the adjusted gross sample or Eligible Respondents as described above), other, potentially systematic, losses need to be addressed more specifically.

In order to do so, the total participant numbers (the realised net sample, see Figure 1) can be split up in groups according to the criteria comprising the sampling frame (e.g. age groups, gender groups, region size groups). The distribution within these groups of the net sample can be statistically adjusted (weighted) to better represent the distribution present in the original gross sample drawn.

An example would be the distribution in the group ,sex': A gross sample for a study originally included, e.g. 200 women and 200 men (leading to a distribution of 50% women and 50% men in the total gross sample of 400). But only 100 women and 150 men participate (comprise the net sample), i.e. leading to a distribution of 40% women and 60% men, instead of 50% each. In this case, the data collected from the women would need to be weighted in more than that of the men in order to represent the original distribution of 50/50 across the original gross sample.

In addition to weighting, there are methods such as multiple imputation, Bayesian data augmentation, expectation-maximization and others (overview in Tolonen (Ed.) 2016) that can be used to estimate potential effects of non-participation.

2.3 Non-responder questionnaire

The non-responder questionnaire lastly is a tool to assess bias in the study population according to certain factors (e.g. their exposure levels). It is a short questionnaire created to document key criteria of the Eligible Respondents that have declined participation (see Figure 1). This serves in order to be able to assess possible (systematic) differences in these key criteria between those that participate and those that decline participation. Using information from the non-response questionnaire, adjustment for non-response bias through statistical modelling is aimed at.

A non-response questionnaire should be designed to contribute to the determination of defined characteristics that influence exposure.

3 Recommendations for the development of non-responder questionnaires

A questionnaire specifically addressed at individuals that have declined participation needs to be designed to take into account and carefully weigh the individual decision for non-participation against the scientific interest in information about exactly those individuals.

Therefore and based on expertise gathered in five rounds of conducting the German Environmental Survey (GerES), non-responder questionnaires should be kept as short and compact as possible to reduce participant burden to an absolute minimum. Wherever possible, questions should be asked in a way that makes it possible to answer with 'Yes', 'No' or 'Don't Know'. 'Refusal' of a single question should also be possible to note.

It is of interest to be able to compare the group of participants that declined participation in the study but who have provided answers to the non-responder questionnaire to those participants that have accepted participation and completed the study. Therefore, questions in a non-responder questionnaire need to be identical or at least highly comparable to those asked in the main (= basic) questionnaire.

As for all questionnaires, it is highly recommended to determine if questions and items in the non-responder questionnaire are well understood and it is generally possible to provide an answer. This can be done, for example, in a pre-test on a small sub-sample of test participants.

The questions comprising a non-responder questionnaire can be split up into two groups, the essential group that should always be considered for inclusion, especially when other sampling frames than national population registers are used, and the group that could be skipped if the participant refuses to spend more time answering the non-responder questionnaire.

In the essential part of the questionnaire, the criteria which led to the original selection of the gross sample need to be included (e.g. age, region, sex) if they are not already known due to the sampling frame (e.g. address or phone number of participant can provide enough information of the region). Questions covering the original sampling criteria are essential, especially when other sampling frames than national population registers are used as these criteria can ensure correct classification of the participant within the gross sample.

The remaining timeframe for questions can then be covered with questions aiming to determine potential exposure of the non-participant to substances or groups thereof of interest. As mentioned above, these questions should be comparable to those in the basic questionnaire and should be reduced to those pathways that highly influence concentration of the substance group(s) of interest or their metabolites the most.

In brief:

- ▶ As short and compact as possible (2-5 minutes maximum) to reduce participant burden to an absolute minimum, if possible: only yes/no/don't know
- ▶ Questions need to be identical or at least highly comparable to those asked in the main questionnaire of the study (e.g. basic questionnaire)
- ▶ Essential questions (especially when other sampling frames than population registers are used): cover criteria which led to the original selection of the gross sample (e.g. age, region, sex)
- ▶ Other questions: cover specific exposure routes, often main path of exposure for the substance (group) of interest

4 Non-responder questionnaire in the scope of HBM4EU

Below you find exemplary questions that could be used to compile a HBM4EU non-responder questionnaire.

Each question is briefly introduced and the rationale behind its selection is explained to give an impression of the reasoning behind the selection of questions for a non-responder questionnaire. Other questions fulfilling the same function could be used as well.

At the same time it has to be noted that these exemplary questions might have to be adjusted if someone provides answers for the participant (e.g. a parent for a child). Also, the reasons for participation (see below 'For what reason did you decline participation in the study?') need to be adjusted according to the study design.

For each study the decision has to be made separately which questions of the basic questionnaire should be transferred to the non-responder questionnaire.

Reply cards can be used in studies to ask for the willingness of the potential participant to participate in the study. These cards can be specifically designed for non-participants and include questions to determine at least a few characteristics about the declining participant. An example for such a reply card can be found in D7.4 '1st material for communication to participants, including informed consent'.

4.1 Questions considered essential for a non-responder questionnaire

What questions are considered essential can vary depending on the intentions of a study. This concept assumes that representativeness is aimed at in the study it is applied in.

Following, the three questions which comprise the essential part of the questionnaire are depicted as examples. As mentioned already in Section 4, sex and age are criteria which are foreseen to be used for the original selection of the gross sample. The criterion 'region' is assumed to already be known due to the possibility of contacting the participant (e.g. address or phone number of participant used to reach him or her with this questionnaire can provide enough information of the region). To save time it is therefore not included as a question.

It could be useful to consider adjusting the basic questionnaire to ask the questions first that have been identified as essential in the non-responder questionnaires. That way, participants that cancel the interview are more likely to have already provided the most important data.

A good introductory question for the non-responder questionnaire is asking for the reason why the participant has declined participation in the study in the first place.

For what reason did you decline participation in the study?	
<u>Interviewer:</u>	Only main reason should be selected.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Absence during the time of the survey
<input type="checkbox"/>	Acutely or chronically ill
<input type="checkbox"/>	No time
<input type="checkbox"/>	Not interested or not convinced by purpose of the survey
<input type="checkbox"/>	Doubts about data protection measures
<input type="checkbox"/>	Too much effort (survey takes too long)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Generally decline participation in surveys
<input type="checkbox"/>	Others, specify: _____
Don't know <input type="checkbox"/> Refused <input type="checkbox"/>	

Rationale behind the question: As mentioned in Section 3.1.2, the question above serves to determine the reason why potential participants decline participation in the study and helps adjusting the sample for loss.

For example, in case of a home visit by the interviewer, one of the reasons for non-participation could be that the potential participant declines participation due to the home visit. This should be adequately reflected in the possible choices of reasons.

What is your sex?	
<u>Interviewer:</u>	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Male
<input type="checkbox"/>	Female
Don't know <input type="checkbox"/> Refused <input type="checkbox"/>	

Rationale behind the question: If sex is one of the selection criteria for the gross sample, it is considered an essential question and should be asked early on in the questionnaire. Sex is also relevant when determining exposure to substances (e.g. phthalates).

What is your birth date?	
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Month	Year
Don't know <input type="checkbox"/> Refused <input type="checkbox"/>	

Rationale behind the question: If age is one of the selection criteria for the gross sample, it is considered an essential question and should be asked early on in the questionnaire. Age is also

potentially relevant when determining exposure to certain substances or substance groups (e.g. phthalates, BPA, PFAS, FR, Cd, Cr, PAHs, anilines).

4.2 Optional or substance-related questions for a non-responder questionnaire

The questions below are exemplary and need to be carefully selected for each study individually, depending on the questions (and their wording) used in the study's basic questionnaire and the substances and substance groups of interest. As elaborated in Section 4, the overall number of questions in a non-responder questionnaire should be kept as small as possible. Due to the fact that in HBM4EU several substances and substance groups have to be covered in all questionnaires, the following selection of questions is quite extensive.

Which fuels or sources of energy are used in your home for heating?

Interviewer: Only **main reason** should be selected.

- Charcoal/Coal
- Wood
- Wood pellets
- Others

Don't know Refused

Rationale behind the question: As they could potentially release smoke indoors, (Char)coal and wood (pellets) used as fuels can be a source of exposure with PAHs. This question serves to briefly address possible PAH exposure in the home and is easy and quick to answer (unlike a more difficult question directed at the traffic outside for which the type of street would have to be determined which could lead to confusion).

In the last 4 weeks, did you consume fast food (please consider also beverages)?

Interviewer: Fast food is commercially prepared, processed food that is ready to eat as a quick meal or for takeaway. Consider also beverages.

- Yes
- No

Refused

Rationale behind the question: Fast food is often packaged with food contact materials possibly containing phthalates, BPA, PFAS and other priority substances. This question requires the additional information of what is meant by 'fast food', but is highly relevant as it is an important exposure pathway for the above mentioned substance groups and therefore included here.

What is the main source of your drinking water?

Interviewer: Only **main reason** should be selected.

- Public network
- Private well

<input type="checkbox"/>	Bottled water (plastic)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Bottled water (glass)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Others		
		Don't know	<input type="checkbox"/> Refused <input type="checkbox"/>

Rationale behind the question: Depending on the source, drinking water can be a source of phthalate and BPA exposure. The origin of drinking water could be also associated with the exposure to PFAS. This question is quick to answer as it requires only one option to be chosen and is relevant for several substance groups.

In relation to smoking habits, which of the following options best describes your situation?

Interviewer: Only **one option** should be selected. Smoking refers to cigarettes, cigars, pipes, and electronic cigarettes.

<input type="checkbox"/>	I have never smoked		
<input type="checkbox"/>	I was a smoker but I gave up smoking		
<input type="checkbox"/>	I currently smoke occasionally		
<input type="checkbox"/>	I currently smoke daily		
		Don't know	<input type="checkbox"/> Refused <input type="checkbox"/>

Rationale behind the question: Smoking is a known source of exposure for substance groups such as PAHs, Cd, Cr, BPA and anilines. This question requires the additional information of which type of smoking is meant here, but is highly relevant for several substance groups and therefore included here.

During the past 48 hrs, did you use any products belonging in one of the following categories?

Interviewer: To help the participant '48 hrs ago is the day before yesterday around this time' can be said. Please note that several options can be selected.

	Used during past 48 hours	Not used during past 48 hours	Don't know
Hair products	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Body care products	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cosmetics	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
			Refused <input type="checkbox"/>

Rationale behind the question: Contact with hair (treatment) products, like dyes, can be a path of exposure for anilines. Humans can also be exposed to phthalates and substitutes as well as BPA when using body care products like body lotion, deodorant, creams and cosmetic products. Specific types of cosmetics, like water-resistant make-up and nail polish could be associated with exposure to PFAS.

What materials is most of the floor covering in your home made of?

Interviewer: Only **main materials** should be selected. Most refers to more than half of the entire floor in all rooms.

- Wood-parquet
- Wooden planks
- Laminate
- PVC
- Linoleum
- Tiles
- Synthetic fibre
- Natural fibre
- Natural or synthetic fibre with plastic backing
- Others

Don't know Refused

Rationale behind the question: The floor covering is considered an important source of indoor exposure to certain compounds, especially phthalates, BPA, PFASs and FR. This question requires the additional information of what 'most of the floor covering' means, but is highly relevant for several substance groups and therefore included here.

4.2.1 Questions potentially causing discomfort for the participant

Questions considered to touch upon private matters such as employment status and weight are purposefully asked at the end of the questionnaire to avoid early cancellation of the interview. Examples of such questions are provided in the following.

How tall are you without shoes (in cm)?

cm

Don't know Refused

How much do you weigh without clothes and shoes (in kg)?

kg

Don't know Refused

Rationale behind the questions: Body weight has been shown to correlate with exposure to certain substances such as phthalates. Height is asked for determination of the Body-Mass-Index. This question is positioned at the end of the questionnaire as it is potentially unpleasant to answer for the participant.

What is the highest level of education you attained?

Interviewer: Only **one option** should be selected.

- No formal education or below primary education (ISCED 0)
- Primary education (ISCED 1)
- Lower secondary education, or second stage of basic education (ISCED 2)
- Upper secondary education (ISCED 3)
- Post-secondary non-tertiary education (ISCED 4)
- Short-cycle tertiary education (ISCED 5)
- Bachelor's or equivalent level (ISCED 6)
- Master's or equivalent level (ISCED 7)
- Doctoral or equivalent level (ISCED 8)

Don't know Refused

What is your current main labour status?

Interviewer: Only **one option** should be selected.

- Employee working full-time
- Employee working part-time
- Self-employed working full-time (including family worker)
- Self-employed working part-time (including family worker)
- Unemployed
- Pupil, student, further training, unpaid work experience
- In retirement or in early retirement or has given up business
- Permanently disabled or/and unfit to work
- In compulsory military community or service
- Fulfilling domestic tasks and care responsibilities
- Other inactive person
- Other status, specify: _____

Don't know Refused

Rationale behind the questions: The questions are used to achieve an impression of the participant's socio-economic situation, which could be used to develop an indicator of occupational social class. SES can be a determinant of exposure to phthalates, PFASs, BPA, FR, Cd, Cr, PAHs and anilines (1st priority substances). This question is positioned at the end of the questionnaire as it is potentially unpleasant to answer for the participant.

4.2.2 Questions directed exclusively at a sub-group of participants

The following question should be addressed at women only:

Are you currently breast-feeding or have breastfed?

Interviewer: Only ask this question to women.

Yes

No

Refused

Rationale behind the questions: Breast feeding history could affect the concentrations of certain compounds in humans (e.g. PFASs, FR). This question is only directed at female participants.

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